

WAYS AND IMPORTANCE OF APPLYING STRATEGIC
MANAGEMENT IN ENTERPRISES

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Abstract. *This article talks about the importance of management in enterprises, its types and ways of applying strategic management. Strategic management is defined as the process by which an organization develops its strategy, which begins with a mission and vision embodied in tangible goals and objectives of the entire company.*

Keywords. *Economy, management, organization, enterprises, company, development, strategic management, competitiveness, profitability.*

The word "strategy" is primarily associated with military history. But in the current competitive era, the success of a company largely depends on the strategic and critical thinking of its management. Organizations face exciting and dynamic challenges in the twentieth century. A sustainable competitive advantage arises when a firm implements a unique value creation strategy. The corporate strategy includes the commitments, decisions and actions necessary for the company to achieve strategic competitiveness and generate profits above average profitability.

An organization with strong strategic planning leads the way among other firms in the industry. Due to the rapid development of the global economy, there is a need for strategic planning and brainstorming. Strong strategic planning and its effective management is crucial to the success of any organization. Strategic

management is a disciplinary approach that uses principles and a management process different from that in classical business.

The effectiveness of any organization's business in a competitive economy largely depends on the quality of its management through the proper implementation of strategic management. Experts define strategic management as the process by which an organization develops its strategy, which begins with a mission and vision embodied in tangible goals and objectives of the entire company.

Strategic management is carried out through strategic analysis and planning, the development of plans, then the implementation of plans and their continuous improvisation takes place to adjust in accordance with environmental changes, after which the implementation and evaluation of the results are carried out.

Thus, together, the following five elements of corporate strategic management ensure business success in today's dynamic business environment.

SWOT analysis is an important stage in the development of the strategic management concept. This analysis is a great way to prepare for the development of a strategic plan. SWOT analysis allows you to assess both the internal strengths and weaknesses of an organization, as well as its capabilities and potential threats imposed by the external environment. Identifying these four essential components of a company's existence is often the main structural element of strategic plans.

Strategic planning is an important component of building a roadmap for an organization's mission and vision for the future. It allows the board of directors and management to assess the current environment, the company's position in this environment, and then develop a plan for the successful fulfillment of the organization's mission. The success of a strategy depends on its constant improvisation. Unlike business plans, there is no one right way to create effective strategic planning.

Because it depends on creativity and out-of-the-box thinking, there is no ideal way to develop a winning strategic plan. The deeper the study of the current state and capabilities of the company is carried out, the more promising and effective the strategic plan can become. Strategic thinking defines the methods that a company will use to achieve its goals.

Strategic management is a topic of great importance for the modern corporate world. The researchers note that strategic management is a tool of a corporate organization to face future challenges and improve long-term goals. Experts also emphasize strategic management as a process during which an organization develops its strategies, which begin with missions and visions, and then formulate and justify corporate goals and objectives.

The strategy not only determines the direction of the company's activities, but also contributes to the success of their achievement. Specialists also determine the need to designate levels of strategic management. Various levels of strategic management, such as corporate strategy, business strategy and functional strategy, play an important role in increasing the productivity of the company. According to the study, corporate strategy increases the potential of an organization in the field of improving the culture of the organization, internal efficiency, communication with customers and, finally, financial performance by increasing the profitability of the company, revenue, reducing costs and risks.

The ability to transform an organization in response to economic changes has also increased and has become a decisive factor for success in a changing environment. The study also identified some other important factors, such as corporate governance, social responsibility and business ethics, that need to be taken into account when adopting a business strategy. A review of the literature also showed that the formulation of a strategy is a very important step, since these strategies are a theoretical corrective approach to solving problems faced by an organization, but their effective implementation is a practical solution to problems.

Thus, organizational excellence can be achieved both by formulating and implementing the right strategies. To facilitate the strategic management process, strategies are formulated and implemented in four levels of strategic planning. These hierarchical levels help organizations achieve both short-term and long-term goals.

Companies engaged in different types of business use separate business strategies for each type of business. Although these strategies may differ from each other, all business strategies of an organization or firm remain under the umbrella of the overall mission, vision and goals of the organization. Functional strategy deals with the implementation of corporate and business strategies. These strategies relate to the steps taken to effectively implement higher-level strategies. He is dealing with a relatively limited plan that provides goals for a specific function of the company.

Functional strategies can be non-quantifiable actions, such as customer satisfaction, or they can also be quantitative actions, such as the volume of orders placed or delivered at a time. The heads of the main functional areas of the business units are responsible for the development and implementation of the functional strategy. Operational strategies are developed at the management level of both the entire company and its departments and set periodic short-term goals for implementation. Such strategies are the responsibility of business leaders, heads of geographic divisions, and lower-level managers.

Different levels of strategies such as corporate strategy, business strategy, functional strategy and operational strategy play an important role in improving the productivity of a firm. Corporate strategy increases the potential of the organization by increasing the culture of the organization, and then internal efficiency, and finally allows you to improve financial performance by increasing profitability, income and reducing costs and risks.

The ability to transform an organization in terms of responding to economic changes has also become a decisive factor for success in a changing environment. In a competitive environment, companies are constantly trying to change their strategies depending on the situation, but if the organization is not adaptive, it will not be able to gain a competitive advantage, and also risks losing market share. Accordingly, in an ever-changing world, corporations should also pay attention to corporate governance, social responsibility and business ethics when developing business strategies. Strategic planning is the process of defining an organization's plans to achieve goals and mission. An organizational strategy is a derivative approach to achieving the above benchmarks. This is a planning activity that covers boundaries and takes into account all elements of the micro and macro environment of the company.

The key objectives of the corporate strategy development and implementation process are:

- ❖ studying and defining the company 's vision for the future;
- ❖ determining the methodology for achieving the goals and objectives of the organization;
- ❖ defining the company's profile, including an internal analysis of the culture, strengths and capabilities of the organization;
- ❖ conducting an analysis of the external environment to identify factors such as threats, opportunities, etc.;
- ❖ figuring out ways to compare the company's profile with its environment in order to be able to fulfill the mission statement;
- ❖ choosing a set of long - term goals and their respective strategies;
- ❖ Implementation of the selected strategies in a planned manner based on budgets and resource allocations, with a statement of action programs and tasks.

Strategic management is a complex and continuous process, it requires hard work and dedication from most people in the organization to move it into the

future. This represents a new focus for the organization; focusing on a compelling vision of the future through continuous brainstorming. In today's competitive world, every organization must prove that it is better than its competitors. So, strategic management can be the key to achieving the desired results of companies in modern conditions.

Accordingly, a competent approach to the organization of work in the field of strategic management and planning is extremely important, since highly competitive markets today create difficult conditions for the functioning of organizations whose task is not only to maintain a favorable market position, but to develop effectively in the future.

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